

irrigated and rainfed conditions: Dular, a tall upland cultivar from Bangladesh; Sufaida Pak, a tall rainfed lowland cultivar from Pakistan; and Newbonnet and Katy, modern semidwarf irrigated rices from the USA. Irrigated plots were flooded to a depth of 5-10 cm throughout the growing season, and nonirrigated plots were watered only once in mid-July when the drought period exceeded 15 d and plants were severely wilted. Plants received 39 cm of rainfall from seeding to maturity.

In experiment one, three-row plots with 40-cm row and hill spacings were handseeded with 15 single-plant hills per row. Six plants were pulled from the middle of the center rows of the irrigated plots at 40 d after seeding (DAS) to measure root pulling resistance (RPR) as a measure of deep root density (Ekanayake et al 1986; Price et al 1990). We used a LI-6200 photosynthesis system (LiCor, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA) to measure photosynthetic rate (Pn) and Stomatal conductance on the second fully opened leaf of five plants from the center row of each plot at 40 DAS. Gas exchange data were taken before noon when plants in dry plots showed mild stress, but the leaves were not rolled yet.

In the second experiment, six-row plots, 4.75 m long, with a 20-cm row

spacing, were drill-seeded with 110 kg seed/ha. Grain yield and other plant characters were observed.

The four cultivars differed in plant height, tiller number, panicle number, growth duration, and RPR values (Table 1). Based on RPR, Dular and Sufaida Pak had larger deep-root systems than Newbonnet and Katy, and Newbonnet had a significantly larger root system than Katy. Significant interactions between cultivars and water regimes in Pn occurred (Table 2).

Dular and Katy had the highest Pn under nonstressed conditions, whereas Newbonnet had the highest under stressed conditions. Stomatal conductance was highest in Katy followed by Newbonnet and Dular under nonstressed conditions (Table 2). In two of our previous experiments, Newbonnet produced higher biomass and grain yields than the other three varieties under drought stress. Although we do not fully understand why, it is possible that Newbonnet can maintain a greater leaf water potential by osmotic adjustment and a greater sink capacity for continued photosynthesis than the other three varieties.

Our study confirms the finding of Fukushima et al (1985) that cultivars differed in photosynthetic efficiency

under drought stress. Rice cultivars possessing better photosynthetic efficiency and larger deep-root systems exist in the germplasm. They can be used as parents for breeding improved upland cultivars that will more efficiently use increased levels of atmospheric CO₂ in photosynthesis and may contribute to reduced CH₄ emissions under upland conditions, thus reducing the degree of potential global warming due to greenhouse gases.

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Table 1. plant height, tillers/m², panicles/m², days to heading, and root-pulling resistance in four rice cultivars. Pine Bluff, Arkansas, USA, 1992.

Cultivar	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/m ² (no.)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Days to heading (d)	Root-pulling resistance (kg)
Dular	120 a ^a	590 b	553 a	71 b	42 a
Katy	97 b	587 b	495 b	91 a	14 c
Newbonnet	95 b	492 c	418 c	90 a	23 b
Sufaida Pak	124 a	622 a	505 b	88 a	39 a
CV (%)	5.1	7.7	7.2	3.1	9.2

^a Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different at the 0.05 probability level: av of 4 replications.

Table 2. Photosynthetic and stomatal conductance rate of four rice cultivars, Pine Bluff, Arkansas, USA, 1992.

Cultivar	Photosynthetic rate (μmol/m ² per s)		Stomatal conductance (mol/m ² per s)	
	Irrigated	Nonirrigated	Irrigated	Nonirrigated
Dular	22.9 a ^a	15.0 c	3.0 b	1.8
Katy	23.5 a	17.9 b	4.1 a	2.5
Newbonnet	19.9 b	22.4 a	3.2 b	2.4
Sufaida Pak	17.3 c	10.9 d	2.3 c	2.2
CV (%)	20.43		24.11	

^a Means with the same letter in a column are not significantly different at the 0.05 probability level: av of 4 replications.

Impact of global warming on rice production in Egypt

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Egypt has an arid, subtropical climate in which rice is grown as one of several summer crops following winter crops. Rice was introduced in Egypt in the northern delta near the Mediterranean Sea, at the end of the irrigation system, for controlling salinity. If global warming occurs, the major concerns in Egypt would be the impacts on water supply, sea level, and growing season.

Water supply. Egypt receives essentially no rain; the Nile River is the country's only water source. This water originates in the headwaters of the Blue Nile in the highlands of Ethiopia, some 4000 km upstream from Egypt's ricefields. If a change in climate reduces the rainfall in Ethiopia, Egypt's water supply will be reduced, which will affect the area of irrigated land. If Ethiopia

receives more rain, Egypt can expand its agricultural land outside of the delta.

Raised Mediterranean Sea level. The low elevation of the lands in the northern delta make them the most vulnerable in Egypt to inundation from rising sea levels. It is estimated that a 2-m rise in sea level would inundate about 50% of the ricelands and a 4-m rise would inundate almost all. Infrastructure to protect the delta is in place, but extensive renovations may be required to accommodate a rise in sea level, including salt water intrusion barricades across the Nile branches, a network of deep drains with pumps to discharge drainage water into the sea, and even construction of a seawall along the 250 km of the delta coast.

A more pressing problem may be reversing the hydrostatic pressure on soil salts. With the current sea level, the flooded ricefields provide a positive hydrostatic pressure to leach salts from the soil. If the sea level rises above the ricelands, the hydrostatic pressure would be reversed and the natural pressure would be for salts to move up in the soil profile. If this happens, rice may become a more important component in the crop rotation and have to be grown more frequently, increasing the water required to protect the land from salinity.

Cropping season. The subtropical climate, with full irrigation, supports an intensive fully double-cropped system, with distinct summer and winter growing seasons. Rice is planted in the spring, as the increasing mean temperature exceeds 20 °C, and is harvested in the fall, when the declining mean temperature returns to 20 °C (Fig. 1). Although the mean temperature is above 20 °C and maximum temperature approaches 35 °C, the mean night temperature is always below 20 °C. These cool temperatures delay maturity in rice by up to 30 d compared with tropical areas. The effect of these seasonal temperatures is a marked decline in yields because planting is delayed (Fig. 2). This is attributed to plants maturing with progressively cooler temperatures. Along with the decline in yield, a significant deterioration in grain quality occurs as the head rice yield declines and broken rice increases.

1. Average minimum and maximum temperatures at Sakha, Egypt.

2. Impact of date of sowing on GZ4120.

If a 5 °C uniform increase in temperature occurs, the following may happen.

- The potential growing season may increase by 10 d in both spring and fall.
- The warmer temperatures during maturity could reduce the rate of yield decline associated with late planting, thus providing higher and more stable average yields. Temperatures exceeding 40 °C, however, could cause sterility and grain shriveling.
- Fewer nights when the minimum temperature drops below 20 °C could reduce the maturity time of rice, allowing earlier planting of winter crops but not double-cropping rice.
- Higher temperatures may result in increased evapotranspiration and water requirements.

Rice production in Egypt could be very sensitive to global warming. While a

warmer climate may increase potential rice yields, there are risks and concerns about Egypt's water supply, inundation if sea level rises, and increased soil salinity. ■

Lipid peroxidation and superoxide dismutase activity in rice leaves as affected by ultraviolet-B radiation

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Enhanced UV-B radiation affects many processes in plants, such as growth, flowering, pigmentation, respiration, photosynthesis, and stomatal behavior. Recent experiments have demonstrated that UV-B treatment had significant effects on lipid peroxidation and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity (Krizek et al 1993) in cucumber leaves.